

FREE EDGE AND SIZE EFFECTS ON FAILURE INITIATION AND ULTIMATE STRENGTH OF LAMINATES CONTAINING A CENTER HOLE

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ABSTRACT

A failure analysis method that includes free edge and size effects was proposed for composite laminates containing a center hole. First, the size effect on the strength of an unnotched coupon specimen under off-axis loading was established based on experimental results. Subsequently, the location of the onset of failure at the hole was determined by comparing the strength of off-axis unnotched specimens with the hoop stress around the hole. The corresponding strength was defined as the initial failure strength. From the specified failure location and stress, subsequent failure progression was performed by classical ply-by-ply laminate failure analysis. Experiments on $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ and $[0/90]_S$ laminates and their off-axis specimens were performed to verify the present method.

Keywords: laminate, strength, hole, hoop stress, failure initiation, damage progression

1. INTRODUCTION

The strength of laminates containing cutouts has been a subject of immense interest as evidenced by the long list of publications on this subject. Various laminate strength prediction methods have been proposed. A good review of papers on this subject was given by Awerbuch and Madhukar [1].

Generally speaking, the existing strength prediction methods can be categorized into three groups. The first method is called the stress fracture model which was initially proposed by Whitney and Nuismer [2]. In this model, a critical length from the cutout must be chosen so that the point stress or the average stress over the critical length is equal to the ultimate stress of the unnotched laminate. Tan [3] extended this concept for more general situations. The main drawback in this method is that the critical length is basically a curve-fitting parameter which could be dependent on the hole size and loading [4].

The second method can be called the equivalent crack method in which a crack is used to represent the initial flaw [5] or to describe the damage progression in the notched laminate [6]. As the form of damage in laminates is quite different from that of an ideal crack, such representation is questionable. At best, the fracture mechanics parameters such as stress intensity factor and strain energy release rate are used as curve-fitting parameters.

The third method is basically a ply-by-ply failure progressive analysis using lamination theory to

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predict failure initiation and ultimate strength of notched laminates [7]. Certain failure criteria are utilized to determine failure and failure modes of each lamina, and some rules are employed to estimate the degradation of the mechanical properties in the damaged region. Because of the limitation of the 2-D nature in lamination theory, the effect of interlaminar stresses on the failure of laminates is not included in the failure analysis.

Chu and Sun [4] introduced a method that includes the free edge effect in the failure analysis of laminates containing a center hole. The essence of this method lies in using unnotched laminate strengths with respect to different loading angles and comparing them with hoop stresses around the hole. From this comparison, the location of failure onset at the hole is determined.

In this study, the effect of hole size is addressed. The size effect of the unnotched coupon specimen used in measuring laminate strength was established first. Utilizing the size effect on the unnotched strength to represent free edge strength around the hole, the initial failure strength for different hole sizes was determined. A lamination theory-based finite element program DPEDGE was developed to simulate the subsequent damage propagation and to estimate the ultimate laminate strength. The analytical predictions were compared with experimental results for AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ and $[0/90]_S$ laminates.

2. STRENGTH OF UNNOTCHED LAMINATES

2.1 Material and Specimen

AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy was used to fabricate the laminates. The ply thickness of the laminate was 0.132 mm. The major mechanical properties of AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite were given by [8] as $E_1 = 139$ GPa, $E_2 = 9.86$ GPa, $G_{12} = 6.21$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.30$, $X = 2.14$ GPa, $Y = 56.5$ MPa, $S = 110.3$ MPa, $X' = -2.01$ GPa, $Y' = -207$ MPa, where E_1 is the longitudinal modulus of elasticity, E_2 is the transverse modulus, G_{12} is the inplane shear modulus, ν_{12} is the longitudinal Poisson's ratio, and X (X'), Y (Y') and S are the longitudinal tensile (compressive), transverse tensile (compressive), and in-plane shear strengths, respectively.

Two types of laminates were considered in the present study, i.e., $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ and $[0/90]_S$ laminates. Specimens were cut along three directions, 0° , 7.5° , and 15° from the panel. These angles are designated as loading angles to the original laminate. For each angle, six different sizes of specimen were considered. The dimensions of these specimens are listed in Table 1.

2.2 Test Results

Tension tests were conducted to determine the ultimate strengths of the specimens. In addition, if initial failure occurred at the free edge before complete laminate failure, the load was also recorded and designated as the failure initiation strength.

Tables 2 and 3 list the test results of failure strengths of specimens with different dimensions for $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ and $[0/90]_S$ laminates, respectively. The results revealed that $[0/90]_S$ laminate specimens and the 0° specimen of the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate failed suddenly, and their ultimate strengths increased as the size of the specimen decreased. On the other hand, in the off-axis $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ specimens (7.5° and 15°) failure was noted to initiate along the free edge and then propagate into the laminate upon increasing loading. Apparently, failure initiation in these specimens was controlled by the free edge stresses. For small volumes, $V/V_0 < 1$, the strengths of these specimens appear to be independent of size.

Table 1. Dimensions of specimen for size effect testing.

Width (mm)	38.1	25.4	12.7	12.7	12.7	12.7
Gate Length (mm)	228.6	228.6	228.6	152.4	114.3	76.2

Table 2. Failure strengths (MPa) of $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate with different dimensions subjected to on- and off-axis loadings. V_0 is the volume of the 25.4 mm \times 228.6 mm specimen.

Loading Angle	Size (V/V_0)					
	0.175	0.275	0.35	0.55	1.0	1.5
0°	742	725	718	707	683	678
7.5°	421	425	418	425	451	478
15°	379	373	381	376	383	411

Table 3. Failure strength (MPa) of $[0/90]_S$ laminate with different dimensions subjected to on- and off-axis loadings. V_0 is the volume of the 25.4 mm \times 228.6 mm specimen.

Loading Angle	Size (V/V_0)					
	0.175	0.275	0.35	0.55	1.0	1.5
0°	1120	1097	1077	1051	1024	1005
7.5°	446	431	425	417	403	396
15°	293	286	284	274	265	268

2.3 Modeling of Size Effect

Following Zweben [9], we assume the relation between strength and volume of the specimen as

$$\frac{\sigma_{ult}}{\sigma_{ult}^0} = \left(\frac{V_0}{V}\right)^{1/m} \quad (1)$$

where σ_{ult}^0 and V_0 are the strength and volume, respectively, of the 25.4 mm wide and 228.6 mm long specimen.

The strength σ_{ult} corresponds to the volume V . From the test data listed in Tables 2 and 3, $\sigma_{ult}/\sigma_{ult}^0$ (σ_{ult}^0 is the 0° -specimen strength) is shown in Figure 1 for different loading angles. A fitting curve is used to extrapolate the data to other loading angles.

Figure 2 shows the curve-fitting results with different values of m in Equation (1) for the $[0/90]_S$ laminate. It is evident that $m = 21$ fits the data very well for all loading angles considered. This value is also valid for the $0^\circ [0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate specimen.

3. FAILURE INITIATION OF NOTCHED LAMINATES

Because of free edge stresses, failure often emanates from the boundary of cutout. Experimental results in [4] indicated clearly that failure initiated from the boundary of the hole. It is then obvious that free edge stresses at the hole boundary must have played an important role in failure initiation. To predict free edge failure, theoretically, the 3-D stress field near the free edge must be obtained first. In addition, failure criteria based on these free edge stresses must be available. Such a procedure would be extremely expensive computationally. Moreover, such analysis may not necessarily be accurate.

In a previous study [4], a new method was proposed for predicting failure initiation in laminates containing a center hole. Initial failure location around the hole was determined based on the comparison of the unnotched laminate strength with the 2-D hoop stress along the hole, thus avoiding the need of the 3-D free edge stresses. In [4], the free edge strengths were based on the test results of 25.4 mm wide 228.6 mm long unnotched coupon specimens. In this study, the size effect on the strength of the unnotched coupon specimen was taken into account.

Figure 1. Strength ratio for σ_{ult}/σ_0 unnotched $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ and $[0/90]_s$ laminates ($25.4 \text{ mm} \times 228.6 \text{ mm}$) subject to off-axis loadings (σ_0 is the strength of 0° specimen).

Figure 2. Strength-size relation for $[0/90]_s$ laminates under 0° , 7.5° and 15° loadings.

3.1 Experimental Procedures

Specimens were cut from the laminate along 0° , 7.5° and 15° directions. A water jet was used to create a center hole in these specimens. The hole diameters were chosen to be 6.35 mm, 9.53 mm, and 12.7 mm. The corresponding widths of the specimens were 24.4 mm, 38.1 mm, and 50.8 mm, respectively. Thus, the width to hole diameter ratio was kept constant for all three sizes of specimen.

The purpose of the test was to find the failure initiation location at the hole, the failure initiation load, and the ultimate strength of the notched laminate. Five notched specimens for each loading angle (0° , 7.5° , 15°) were tested in tension. The first notched specimen was loaded monotonically to final failure to obtain ultimate strength. For the $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ laminate, the second specimen was loaded at small load steps starting at 20% of ultimate strength with 5% increments until reaching 40% of ultimate strength.

At each load step, an X-ray radiography was taken to examine the initiation of failure and the subsequent propagation. Initial failure was found to occur near the 40% load level. Subsequent load levels were 60%, 80%, 90%, and 95% which would reveal damage propagation characteristics. With the damage initiation load level obtained from the second specimen, load levels for the remaining three specimens were chosen to be 35%, 40%, 60%, 80%, 90%, and 95%.

For the notched $[0/90]_S$ specimens the same procedure was used to determine failure initiation location and strength as well as damage progression behavior. The load steps were chosen as 40%, 50%, 60%, 70%, 80%, 90%, and 95% of the ultimate strength of the notched specimen.

It is conceivable that the precise location of damage initiation based on the radiographs is very difficult due to the small size of the hole and the finite size of the damage. Thus, a range in angular position along the hole boundary was used to indicate the failure initiation location. Tables 4 and 5 list the failure initiation locations in the first quadrant of the specimen for $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ and $[0/90]_S$ laminates, respectively. It is evident that failure does not initiate at the maximum hoop stress location.

The average failure initiation loads are presented in Tables 6 and 7.

Table 4. Location of failure initiation in the first quadrant of the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate containing different hole size under on- and off-axis loadings. Definition of θ_1 is given by Figure 3.

Loading Angle Specimen	Location of Failure Initiation (θ_1)					
	0°		7.5°		15°	
	Exp.	Pred.	Exp.	Pred.	Exp.	Pred.
50.8 mm width	9°		0°		-4°	
12.7 mm hole		10.5°		3.75°		-3.0°
38.1 mm width	12°		8°		0°	
9.53 mm hole		10.5°		3.75°		-3.0°
25.4 mm width	9°		0°		-7°	
6.35 mm hole	14°		10°		0°	
	6°		-2°		-8°	
		10.5°		3.75°		-3.0°
	18°		12°		4°	

Table 5. Location of failure initiation in the first quadrant of the $[0/90]_S$ laminate containing different hole size under on- and off-axis loadings. Definition of θ_1 is given by Figure 3.

Loading Angle Specimen	Location of Failure Initiation (θ_1)					
	0°		7.5°		15°	
	Exp.	Pred.	Exp.	Pred.	Exp.	Pred.
50.8 mm width	9°		2°		-4°	
12.7 mm hole		11.5°		5°		-2.0°
38.1 mm width	13°		8°		0°	
9.53 mm hole		11.5°		5°		-2.0°
25.4 mm width	10°		3°		-7°	
6.35 mm hole	14°		10°		2°	
	10°		0°		-7°	
		11.5°		5°		-2.0°
	16°		12°		3°	

Table 6. Failure initiation loads σ_{Ni}^{∞} (MPa) of $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminates containing different hole size under on- and off-axis loadings.

Loading Angle Specimen	Strength of Failure Initiation (σ_{Ni}^{∞}) (MPa)					
	0°		7.5°		15°	
	Exp.	Pred.	Exp.	Pred.	Exp.	Pred.
12.7 mm hole	165	148	149	139	140	135
9.53 mm hole	168	148	147	139	140	135
6.35 mm hole	166	148	149	139	141	135

Table 7. Damage initiation size a_0 that provided k_{\min} for $[0/90]_s$ laminates containing different size hole under on- and off-axis loadings.

Loading Angle ϕ	Initial Damage Size a_0 (mm)		
	0°	7.5°	15°
12.7 mm hole	0.474	0.441	0.380
9.53 mm hole	0.355	0.331	0.283
6.35 mm hole	0.237	0.220	0.189

3.2 Prediction of Failure Initiation

Consider a notched laminate subjected to uniform stress σ_N^∞ as shown in Figure 3. At a point located at θ_1 on the hole boundary, the loading angle ψ of the hoop stress is given by (see Figure 3)

$$\psi = \theta_1 + \phi \quad (2)$$

It is assumed that failure would occur if

$$\sigma_{\text{ult}}(\psi, a_0) = \bar{\sigma}_{\theta\theta}(\theta_1, \phi, a_0) \quad (3)$$

where σ_{ult} is the unnotched laminate strength for loading angle ψ , and $\bar{\sigma}_{\theta\theta}$ is the average hoop stress over the region $r = a$ to a_0 :

$$\bar{\sigma}_{\theta\theta}(\theta_1, \phi, a_0) = \frac{1}{a_0 - a} \int_a^{a_0} \sigma_{\theta\theta}(\theta_1, \phi, r) dr \quad (4)$$

where a is the radius of hole, and a_0 indicates the size of initial failure.

Since the laminate strength varies around the hole, the failure location, in general, does not coincide with the location of maximum hoop stress. Instead, we examine the strength/stress ratio

$$\frac{\sigma_{\text{ult}}/\sigma_o}{\bar{\sigma}_{\theta\theta}/\sigma_N^\infty} = k(\theta_1, \phi, a_0) \quad (5)$$

and find the θ_1 and size a_0 that produce the minimum value of k for a given ϕ . In Equation (5), σ_o is the strength of the unnotched 0° specimen of size 25.4 mm \times 228.6 mm. In other words, $\sigma_o = \sigma_{\text{ult}}^o$ for the 0° specimen.

In order to determine σ_{ult} at any location θ_1 , the effective volume V must be determined. We take

$$V = a_0^2 h \quad (6)$$

where h is the thickness of the laminate.

Theoretically, $k(\theta_1, \phi, a_0)$ in Equation (5) should be minimized simultaneously with respect to θ_1 and a_0 for a given ϕ . However, based on the results presented in Tables 4-5, the failure initiation location seems to be independent of the hole size. Hence, the failure initiation location θ_1 is first determined by minimizing the following ratio

$$\frac{\sigma_{\text{ult}}^o/\sigma_o}{\sigma_{\theta\theta}/\sigma_N^\infty} = k_o(\theta_1, \phi) \quad (7)$$

Once the location θ_1 is obtained, the value of a_0 is obtained by minimizing k in Equation (5). In view of Equation (3), the failure initiation load for the notched laminate is then obtained from Equation (5) as

Figure 3. Coordinates for a composite laminate containing a center hole.

$$\sigma_{Ni}^{\infty} = \sigma_0 k_{\min} \quad (8)$$

3.3. Prediction and Comparison

In the analysis of the hoop stress $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$, the laminate is assumed to be of infinite in-plane dimensions. The solution is given by Lekhnitskii [10].

For the $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate, the unnotched laminate strength is controlled by free edge stresses and is independent of size. Thus, Equation (7) is used to determine both the failure initiation load and location. The predictions are compared with experimental results in Table 4 for location and in Table 6 for failure initiation load. The experimental data in Table 6 indicate that failure initiation load in the notched $[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate is not influenced by the hole size.

For the $[0/90]_S$ laminate, the unnotched laminate strength exhibits strong size dependency. Equation (5) is used to determine the failure initiation load. First, Equation (7) is used to find the failure initiation location θ_1 . The results are listed in Table 5. Subsequently, the damage size a_0 is found by minimizing k in Equation (5). The results are given in Table 7. It is noted that the value of a_0 depends on the hole radius a , and that a linear relation can be established as

$$a_0 = c a \quad (9)$$

where $c = 13.36, 14.45$ and 16.78 corresponding to $\phi = 0^\circ, 7.5^\circ$ and 15° , respectively.

Table 8 lists the predicted failure initiation loads in the notched $[0/90]_S$ laminates under $0^\circ, 7.5^\circ$ and 15° loadings. Comparison with the experimental results indicates that the predictions are fairly accurate.

Table 8. Failure initiation loads σ_{Ni}^{∞} (MPa) of $[0/90]_S$ laminates containing different hole size under on- and off-axis loadings.

Loading Angle	Strength of Failure Initiation (σ_{Ni}^{∞}) (MPa)					
	0°		7.5°		15°	
Specimen	Exp.	Pred.	Exp.	Pred.	Exp.	Pred.
12.7 mm hole	207	204	168	170	143	145
9.53 mm hole	217	210	182	177	151	150
6.35 mm hole	243	221	196	188	160	161

4. DAMAGE PROGRESSION AND FINAL FAILURE

Analysis of damage progression after initiation of failure followed the procedure established in [4]. The 4-node isoparametric plane stress finite element derived based on classical lamination theory was used for stress analysis. It is important to note that damage propagation from the initial failure location may stop after a certain level of loading, and a new damage may begin from another location at the hole. This latter damage often leads to the final failure of the laminate. The initial failure has the effect of reducing the hoop stress around the damaged hole.

The procedure of analysis is briefly summarized as follows.

- 1) At the failure initiation load, the finite element which was inside the initial damage region (a_0) at the failure initiation location was assumed to have failed. This was accomplished by setting all ply stiffnesses to zero.
- 2) After allowing initial failure, surface matrix cracking in the top and bottom layers was assumed to exist in the element adjacent to the initially failed element along the fiber-direction. This was accomplished by setting $E_2 = G_{12} = 0$ in the top and bottom layers.
- 3) The subsequent failure analysis consisted of three parts. The first part was for the elements at the hole edge. For these elements, failure was assumed to occur if the hoop stress ($\sigma_{\theta\theta}$) reached the free edge strength (σ_{ult}) of the corresponding unnotched coupon specimen. The free edge strength utilized for the element around the hole was the strength at damage region a_0 . As a result, the size effect on the unnotched laminate strength was taken into account. Note that in this analysis the material properties of failed elements were modified by setting the top and bottom ply stiffnesses to zero, and setting E_2 and $G_{12} = 0$ for the remaining plies. This was based on experimental observation.

The second part of the analysis was for the elements covering the interior portion of the laminate. In this part, failure was assumed to be dominated by inplane stress. Thus, the classical ply-by-ply stiffness discounting procedure using Hill-Tsai criterion and classical laminate theory was adopted.

The last part was for the element with surface crack adjacent to the initially failed elements along the top surface fiber direction. Within this element, if the layer adjacent to the surface layers incurs matrix shear failure, the top and bottom layers were assumed to have delaminated. Then, the surface matrix cracking was assumed to propagate to the element adjacent to the surface delaminated element along the fiber direction. Hill-Tsai ply-by-ply failure criterion was also utilized in this part of the analysis.

The analysis results for the ultimate laminate strengths of the notched $[0/90]_s$ laminate are presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Ultimate stresses of $[0/90]_s$ laminates containing a center hole under on- and off-axis loadings.

Off-Axis Angle	Ultimate Strength (MPa)					
	0°		7.5°		15°	
Specimen	Pred.	Exp.	Pred.	Exp.	Pred.	Exp.
50.8 mm width with 12.7 mm hole	621	643	268	294	168	180
38.1 mm width with 9.32 mm hole	621	643	280	308	172	186
25.4 mm width with 6.35 mm hole	621	653	294	327	175	187

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the analytical and experimental results, the following conclusions were obtained.

- Free edge strength around the hole in the composite laminate can be estimated from the strength of unnotched coupon specimens cut from the laminate in various directions. Failure occurs at a point on the hole boundary when the hoop stress is equal to the corresponding strength of the unnotched coupon specimen.
- The size effect on the strength of unnotched off-axis specimens is formulated by Equation 1. From the experimental test results, it was found that if laminate failure is controlled by inter-laminar failure ($[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate under off-axis loading), the size effect cannot be modeled by Equation 1. It was also found that the initial failure strength in this kind of laminate is independent of specimen size. However, if laminate failure is due to inplane failure ($[0/90/\pm 45]_S$ laminate under on-axis loading and $[0/90]_S$ laminate under on- and off-axis loadings), Equation 1 can be utilized to represent the size effect on the strength of laminates.
- Utilizing the size effect on unnotched strength to represent free edge strength around the hole, the initial failure strength (σ_{Ni}^{∞}) with respect to hole size can be determined. The predicted initial failure loads of laminates containing different hole sizes agree with the experimental data quite well.
- The finite element model is capable of capturing the damage propagation and estimating the final failure strength of the notched laminate. The predicted ultimate strengths with respect to different hole sizes agree with the test data fairly well.

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REFERENCES

1. Awerbuch, J. and Madhukar, M. S., "Notched Strength of Composite Laminates: Predictions and Experiments - A Review," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol. 4, Jan. 1985, pp. 3-159.
2. Whitney, J. M. and Nuismer, R. J., "Stress Fracture Criterion for Laminated Composites Containing Stress Concentrations," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 8, July 1974, p. 253.
3. Tan, S. C., "Laminated Composites Containing an Elliptical Opening. I. Approximate Stress Analyses and Fracture Models," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 21, 1987, pp. 925-948.
4. Chu, G. D. and Sun, C. T., "Failure Initiation and Ultimate Strength of Composite Laminates Containing a Center Hole," *ASTM STP, American Society for Testing and Materials*, 1992, Submitted for publication.
5. Waddoups, M. E., Eisenmann, J. R., and Kaminski, B. E., "Macroscopic Fracture Mechanics of Advanced Composite Materials," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 5, 1971, p. 446.
6. Backlund, J. and Aronsson, C. G., "Tensile Fracture of Laminates with Holes," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 20, July 1986, pp. 259-307.
7. Chang, K. Y., Liu, S. and Chang, F. K., "Damage Tolerance of Laminated Composites Containing an Open Hole and Subjected to Tensile Loadings," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1991, pp. 274-301.
8. Sun, C. T. and Zhou, S. G., "Failure of Quasi-Isotropic Composite Laminates with Free Edges under Off-axis Loading," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol. 7, Nov. 1988, pp. 515-557.
9. Zweben, C. "The Effect of Stress Nonuniformity and Size on the Strength of Composite Materials," *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol. 4, 1972, pp. 1-8.
10. Lekhnitskii, S. G. *Anisotropic Plates*, translated from the second Russian edition by S. W. Tsai and T. Cheron, Gordon and Breach, 1968.